

CIRCUMFERENTIAL RATIO

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RESUMO

Nome: Razão Circunferencial

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Aqui apresentamos equações e fórmulas matemáticas alternativas para a realização do cálculo de circunferências e suas propriedades, com a intenção de simplificar, se possível, o tradicional, sem ser totalmente independente deste.

Palavras-chave: matemática, circunferência, constante, geometria.

ABSTRACT

Name: Circumferential Ratio

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Here we present alternative mathematical equations and formulas for performing the calculation of circles and their properties, with the intention of simplifying, if possible, the traditional one, without being totally independent of it.

Keywords: mathematics, circumference, constant, geometry.

1. Introduction

For this work, calculations were performed in order to obtain a constancy and standard in circumference values. We will demonstrate how we arrived at the Number of Matos (m), and formulas and equations for its possible application, in order to assist traditional calculations with π .

An investigation was made as to a possible standardization in circles, as has been said. Area and perimeter (length) values were taken to carry out this project. Below we will demonstrate how we arrived at the solution.

2. Calculations made to arrive at the solution

We started our work by performing traditional calculations of circumference area and length, making them with circles of consecutive radius size. The following is a sample:

For $r = 2$, we have:

$$A = \pi \cdot 4$$

$$A \approx 12,56$$

$$C = 4 \cdot \pi$$

$$C \approx 12,56$$

For $r = 3$, we have:

$$A = \pi \cdot 9$$

$$A \approx 28,27$$

$$C = 6\pi$$

$$C \approx 18,84$$

For $r = 4$, we have:

$$A = 16\pi$$

$$A \approx 50,26$$

$$C = 8\pi$$

$$C \approx 25,13$$

For $r = 5$, we have:

$$A = 25\pi$$

$$A \approx 78,53$$

$$C = 10\pi$$

$$C \approx 31,41$$

For $r = 6$, we have:

$$A = 36\pi$$

$$A \approx 113,09$$

$$C = 12\pi$$

$$C \approx 37,69$$

If we divide each area by the corresponding length, we have the following:

$$\text{para } r = 2; 1$$

$$\text{para } r = 3; 1,5$$

$$\text{para } r = 4; 2$$

$$\text{para } r = 5; 2,5$$

$$\text{para } r = 6; 3$$

Note that each value obtained is greater $\frac{1}{2}$ than the previous one, $\forall r \in \mathbb{N}$.

With this, we obtain the following numerical expression, which falls into this observation:

$$\frac{A}{C} - [(r - 1) \cdot 0,5] \tag{1}$$

Refining, we have:

$$\frac{A}{C} - \frac{r - 1}{2} \tag{2}$$

From there, we can rearrange the principle described in order to be clearer and more recognizable:

$$\frac{\pi r^2}{2\pi r} - \frac{r - 1}{2}$$

And this is the definition of the Number of Matos (m):

$$m = \frac{\pi n^2}{2\pi n} - \frac{n - 1}{2} = 0,5 \tag{3}$$

3. Possible Applications

A formula proposed for application is precisely the substitution of terms of [1], with the following:

$$\frac{A}{C} - m(r - 1) = 0,5 \tag{4}$$

In this way, with two of the elements described — namely, area, length and radius — known, it becomes possible to ascertain the value of the third party, performing the appropriate resolution process. The following example is observed:

We have a circle, with a diameter measuring 22 meters. We intend to calculate the area and length of this circle.

We'll use the traditional formula to calculate the length. We have the following, therefore:

$$C = 2\pi r$$

$$C = 22\pi$$

$$C \approx 69,11$$

Now, to calculate the area, we will use the formula [4]:

$$\frac{A}{69,11} - 5,5 + 0,5 = 0,5$$

$$\frac{A}{69,11} = 5,5$$

$$A = 5,5 \cdot 69,11$$

$$A \approx 380,10$$

According to the elaborate formula, we have $A \approx 380,1$. Now, we will do a mathematical proof test to find out if, with the traditional formula for area, the results match

$$A = \pi r^2$$

$$A = 121\pi$$

$$A \approx 380,13$$

Here, we observe that the results add up with almost impressive accuracy. There was about 0.03 difference between them, probably due to irregularities in the calculation of π — in its condition of irrational constant.

4. Conclusion

We have tried to present a method for solving calculations involving properties of the circumference that are more accessible than the traditional ones, but that does not replace this one, since it still depends on the Archimedes Constant (π). We perform this mathematical demonstration with highly accurate results that are compatible with the results of traditional calculations.